

Studies on *N,N'*-[2,2'-bis-thienylmethylidene]tolylene

Angela Kriza^a, Cezar Spinu^{b*} and Carmen Pirnau^a

^aDepartment of Inorganic Chemistry, University of Buchares, Bucharest, Romania

^bDepartment of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, University of Craiova, A. I. Cuza 13, Romania

Fax : 40-51-197048

Manuscript received 5 September 2000, accepted 16 December 2000

Cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of the types $MLCl_2$ [where $M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and $L = N,N'$ -(2,2'-bis-thienylmethylidene)tolylene] have been prepared and characterized. Elemental analysis suggests the stoichiometry to be 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (metal : ligand). Magnetic susceptibility data coupled with electronic and ESR spectra suggest a tetrahedral structure for the $MLCl_2$ and CoL_2Cl_2 complexes and square-planar geometry for the NiL_2Cl_2 and CuL_2Cl_2 complexes. IR and NMR spectra of the complexes agree with the coordination to the central metal atom through both the nitrogen atoms. Conductance measurements suggest the nonelectrolytic nature of the $MLCl_2$ complexes and the 1 : 2 electrolytic nature of the ML_2Cl_2 compounds.

Metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde are studied extensively due to synthetic flexibility of these compounds and their selectivity as well as sensitivity towards the central metal atom. In continuation of our work on these complexes¹, we report here the results of our studies on the complexes of Schiff base obtained through condensation of 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde (2-TFCA) and tolylene (TL), *N,N'*-[2,2'-bis-thienylmethylidene]tolylene (TNATL). The presence of four potential donor atoms should render TNATL a versatile ligand. We have synthesized and examined the donor characteristics of this new ligand towards chlorides of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} .

Results and Discussion

The complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with *N,N'*-[2,2'-bis-thienylmethylidene]tolylene have high melting point. They are insoluble in methanol, ethanol and chloroform and more soluble in acetone and DMF.

N,N'-[2,2'-Bis-thienylmethylidene]tolylene (TNATL)

Based on the elemental analysis the formulas $MLCl_2$ and ML_2Cl_2 ($M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$ and Cu^{II}) have been suggested. The molar conductivity data indicate the nonelectrolytic nature for $MLCl_2$ complexes and 1 : 2 electrolytic nature of ML_2Cl_2 complexes (Table 1).

The IR spectrum of the ligand exhibits a band at 1670 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_{C=N}$ of the azomethine group. This band shifts to lower region by about 40–60 cm^{-1} on com-

plexation suggesting coordination through nitrogen atoms of the azomethine group. The medium intensity band at 900

Table 1 Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd	M p °C	Colour	μ_{eff} B M	$\Lambda_{M^{2+}}$ ($\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$)
$L \cdot C_{17}H_{14}N_2S_2$	214	Brown	—	—
$CoLCl_2$	230	Green	4.63	14.5
$NiLCl_2$	179	Brown	3.61	7.6
$CuLCl_2$	250	Brown	2.24	10.4
CoL_2Cl_2	205	Royal blue	4.40	125.8
NiL_2Cl_2	190	Red	Diam	118.5
CuL_2Cl_2	240	Orange	1.73	134.6

*All complexes gave satisfactory metal, S, N and Cl analyses

**In DMF solution ($10^{-3} M$)

cm^{-1} observed in free ligand spectrum, ascribed to ν_{CSC} stretching vibration, appears in the spectra of the complexes at 894–898 cm^{-1} . Also, the bands at 700 and 640 cm^{-1} assigned to the symmetric and asymmetric ν_{CS} are not affected appreciably in the metal complexes, indicating that the sulfur atoms are not involved in coordination. The prove of coordination to the nitrogen atoms is provided by the occurrence of the new bands at 415–426 cm^{-1} (M–N) in the spectra of all the complexes.

In the 1H NMR spectrum of the ligand, the formation of Schiff base is supported by the presence of a peak at δ 9.2 corresponding to the azomethine proton, and a peak at 160.7 ppm in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum, assigned to the azomethine carbon. In case of NiL_2Cl_2 , these signals show a distinct downfield shifts by nearly 0.8 ppm in 1H NMR spectrum, and 5.0 ppm in ^{13}C NMR spectrum, clearly demonstrating the coordination of TNATL via the nitrogen atoms.

UV spectrum of the ligand reveals two absorption bands at 41346 and 36230 cm^{-1} assigned to the transitions $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, respectively. These transitions are also found in the spectra of the complexes but shifted to lower frequencies ($\Delta\nu = 1300\text{--}2500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), confirming the coordination of the ligand to the metal ions.

The electronic spectra of the cobalt(II) complexes are similar. In the $\text{Co}(\text{TNATL})\text{Cl}_2$ complex, the band obtained near 16535 cm^{-1} is assignable to the transition ${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$, which corresponds to a tetrahedral geometry. Further, the observed splitting of this band suggests the distorted tetrahedral symmetry². The magnetic moment values (4.6–4.7 B.M.) support distorted tetrahedral structure³. The royal blue $\text{Co}(\text{TNATL})_2\text{Cl}_2$ complex contains a very intense band at 16300 cm^{-1} , suggestive of tetrahedral geometry, which is also confirmed by the magnetic moment (4.4 B.M.) characteristic of tetrahedral species.

In the $\text{Ni}(\text{TNATL})\text{Cl}_2$ compound, the presence of two bands at 17500 and 10050 cm^{-1} is ascribed to the transitions ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ and ${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3A_2$, which are characteristic to the tetrahedral environment around nickel(II) ion. The value of the magnetic moment (3.61 B.M.) confirms that structure. The $\text{Ni}(\text{TNATL})_2\text{Cl}_2$ complex is diamagnetic suggesting a square-planar environment around Ni^{II} , which is also supported by their visible spectrum at 21340 and 17100 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ transitions, respectively, in a planar arrangement of ligand molecules around Ni^{II} atom^{3,4}.

The electronic spectrum of the $\text{Cu}(\text{TNATL})\text{Cl}_2$ compound exhibits only one broad asymmetric band at 19230 cm^{-1} . This band can be assigned to ${}^2T_2 \rightarrow {}^2E_2$ transition, which is characteristic to the distorted tetrahedral geometry. The magnetic moment lies in the region expected for tetrahedral complexes. This compound presents a very intensive ESR spectrum with parameter $g = 2.146$ which confirms the tetrahedral geometry. The $\text{Cu}(\text{TNATL})_2\text{Cl}_2$ complex displays bands at 18560 and 15280 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transitions in a square-planar stereochemistry⁵. The ESR spectrum of the complex (measured in polycrystalline sample at room temperature) gives g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values in the range 2.150 and 2.07, respectively. The value $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$ is well consistent with a primarily $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state having a square-planar structure⁶.

The molar conductance of the complexes in DMF ($10^{-3} M$) are in the range 7.6–14.5 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for the MLCl_2 complexes, indicating their nonelectrolytic nature, and 118.5–134.6 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ for the ML_2Cl_2 compounds which are 1 : 2-electrolytes.

Experimental

$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.99%), $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.99%), $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.99%), thiophenecarboxaldehyde (98%) (all Merck) and tolylene were used.

Schiff bases : A mixture of ethanolic solutions of 2-TFCA (0.002 mol, 25 ml) and TL (0.001 mol, 25 ml) was refluxed for 10 h on a water-bath. After the concentration of the solution, the resulting precipitate was washed with ethanol and dried over CaCl_2 in vacuum : ${}^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ 9.2; ${}^{13}\text{C NMR } \delta$ 160.7.

MLCl_2 complexes : To an hot ethanolic solution of the metal chlorides were added an hot ethanolic solution of 2-TFCA (0.002 mol, 50 ml) and TL (0.002 mol, 50 ml) in ethanol. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 8–10 h. The resulting solids were washed with ethanol and dried over CaCl_2 in vacuum. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

ML_2Cl_2 complexes : A mixture of 2-TFCA (0.004 mol, 50 ml) and TL (0.002 mol, 50 ml) in ethanol was added to an ethanolic solution of the metal chlorides (0.002 mol, 50 ml). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 12–16 h. The excess of solvent was then distilled. The compounds separated were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over CaCl_2 in vacuum : ${}^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ 9.9; ${}^{13}\text{C NMR } \delta$ 165.7. All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

The ligand and complexes were analyzed for metal, S and Cl by a conventional methods⁷, while C, H and N by microanalytical methods. IR spectra (KBr) were obtained on a BIO-RAD FTS 135 spectrophotometer, UV-VIS spectra (DMF) on a UNICAM UV-4 spectrophotometer, ${}^1\text{H NMR}$ spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian T60 instrument and ${}^{13}\text{C NMR}$ spectra on a Bruker WH 270 spectrometer. The ESR spectra of polycrystalline sample were recorded on a ART 5 spectrometer at room temperature. The magnetic moments were determined by the Faraday method. A K 612 conductivity meter was used to measure the molar conductivities.

References

1. A. Kriza, C. Spinu and M. Pleniceanu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **76**, 82; C. Spinu and A. Kriza, *Acta Chim. Slov.*, 2000, **47**, 179.
2. M. H. Sonar and A. S. R. Murthy, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1977, **108**, 1243; C. Preti and G. Tosi, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1976, **54**, 85.
3. B. N. Figgis, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", Interscience, New York, 1967.
4. B. N. Kashari and L. K. Mishra, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 883; A. Nicolac and O. Maior, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1990, **41**, 223.
5. H. B. Gray and C. J. Balhausen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260; K. Dey and D. Bandyopadhyaya, *India J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 34.
6. B. T. Hathaway, *Struct. Bonding*, 1973, **14**, 60.
7. A. Steyemark and R. Calancertle, *J. Assoc. Anal. Chem.*, 1972, **55**, 680.